

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 19th – 25th October 2020

www.covid19bibliometrics.org

A. Medicine and Health

October 23, 2020 (The Lancet Resp. Medicine)

Ventilation management and clinical outcomes in invasively ventilated patients with COVID-19 (PRoVENT-COVID): a national, multicentre, observational cohort study.

Michael Botta, Anissa M Tsonas, Janesh Pillay et al.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(20\)30459-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(20)30459-8)

PRoVENT-COVID is a national, multicentre, retrospective observational study done at 18 intensive care units (ICUs) in the Netherlands. The authors assessed 553 COVID-19 adult patients who required invasive ventilation. The authors found that in patients with COVID-19 who were invasively ventilated, lung-protective ventilation with low tidal volume and low driving pressure was broadly applied and prone positioning was often used. The findings of this national study provide a basis for new hypotheses and sample size calculations for future trials of invasive ventilation for COVID-19. These data could also help in the interpretation of findings from other studies of ventilation practice and outcomes in invasively ventilated patients with COVID-19.

October 23, 2020 (Science)

Inborn errors of type I IFN immunity in patients with life-threatening COVID-19
Qian Zhang, Paul Bastard, Zhiyong Liu et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abd4570>

The complex immune system involves many genes, including those that encode cytokines known as interferons (IFNs). Individuals who lack specific IFNs can be more susceptible to infectious diseases. Additionally, the autoantibody system dampens IFN response to prevent damage from pathogen-induced inflammation. Q. Zhang et al. used a candidate gene approach and identified patients with severe COVID-19 who have mutations in genes involved in the regulation of type I and III IFN immunity. They found enrichment of these genes in patients and conclude that genetics may determine the clinical course of infection.

October 23, 2020 (Science)

Autoantibodies against type I IFNs in patients with life-threatening COVID-19
Paul Bastard Lindsey B. Rosen, Qian Zhang et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abd4585>

The complex immune system involves many genes, including those that encode cytokines known as interferons (IFNs). Individuals who lack specific

IFNs can be more susceptible to infectious diseases. Additionally, the autoantibody system dampens IFN response to prevent damage from pathogen-induced inflammation. Bastard et. al. identified individuals with high titres of neutralizing autoantibodies against Type IFN- α 2 and IFN- ω about 10% of patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia. These autoantibodies were not found either asymptomatic infected individuals or in healthy individuals. These results provide a means of identifying individuals at risk of developing life-threatening COVID-19.

October 22 2020 (The Lancet Inf. Diseases)

The temporal association of introducing and lifting non-pharmaceutical interventions with the time-varying reproduction number R of SARS-CoV2: a modelling study across 131 countries.

You Li, Harry Campbell, Durga Kulkarni et al.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1472-3099\(20\)30785-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1472-3099(20)30785-4)

This article estimates the effect of introducing and lifting physical distancing measures on COVID-19 reproduction R number. The modelling analysis of non-pharmaceutical interventions in 131 countries – including school and workplace closure, public events ban, ban on gatherings of over 10 people, stay at home orders and internal movement limits – suggests they are associated with the reduced transmission of SARS-CoV2 but there is a 1 – 3 week delay in the effect of imposing or lifting restrictions on the R number. The study also looks at 4 combinations of measures, confirming that combined measures are likely to reduce the R more than individual measures. However, the authors note that their study was not able to account for other potentially influential factors, like mask-wearing and non-compliance with measures.

October 21, 2020 (NEJM)

Efficacy of Tocilizumab in Patients Hospitalized with COVID-19

John H. Stone, Matthew J. Frigault, Naomi J. Serling-Boyd et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2028836>

The efficacy of tocilizumab was tested in a randomized, controlled trial involving patients with COVID-19 who had a fever, pulmonary infiltrates, or a need for supplemental oxygen. The treatment had no significant effect on disease progression, independence from supplemental oxygen, or death. Some benefit or harm cannot be ruled out, however, because the confidence intervals for efficacy comparisons were wide.

October 20, 2020 (JAMA Int. Med.)

Association Between Early Treatment With Tocilizumab and Mortality Among Critically Ill Patients with COVID-19

Shruti Gupta, Wei Wang, Salim S. Hayek et. al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.6252>

This multicentre cohort study assesses mortality rates among patients with COVID-19 admitted to intensive care who were treated with tocilizumab. The authors found that early treatment with tocilizumab may reduce mortality, although the findings may be susceptible to unmeasured confounding, and further research from randomized clinical trials is needed.

October 20, 2020 (JAMA Int. Med.)

Effect of Tocilizumab vs Standard Care on Clinical Worsening in Patients Hospitalized With COVID-19 Pneumonia: A Randomized Clinical Trial
Carlo Salvarani, Giovanni Dolci, Marco Massari et. al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.6615>

This randomized clinical trial evaluates the effect of early tocilizumab administration vs standard therapy in preventing clinical worsening in patients hospitalized with COVID-19.

September 18, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in a cat owned by a COVID-19 - affected patient in Spain

Joaquim Segales, Mariona Puig, Jordi Rodon et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2010817117>

SARS-CoV-2 is considered a zoonotic pathogen mainly transmitted human to human. Few reports indicate that pets may be exposed to the virus. The present report describes a cat suffering from severe respiratory distress and thrombocytopenia living with a family with several members affected by COVID-19. Clinical signs of the cat prompted humanitarian euthanasia and a detailed postmortem investigation to assess whether a COVID-19-like disease was causing the condition. Necropsy results showed the animal suffered from feline hypertrophic cardiomyopathy and severe pulmonary oedema and thrombosis. SARS-CoV-2 RNA was only detected in the nasal swab, nasal turbinates, and mesenteric lymph node, but no evidence of histopathological lesions compatible with a viral infection was detected. The cat seroconverted against SARS-CoV-2, further evidencing a productive infection in this animal. They conclude that the animal had a subclinical SARS-CoV-2 infection concomitant to unrelated cardiomyopathy that led to euthanasia.

B. Science and Engineering

October 1, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

The turning point and end of an expanding epidemic cannot be precisely forecast

Mario Castro, Saul Ares, Jose A. Cuesta et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2007868117>

The authors argue that The turning point and end of an expanding epidemic cannot be precisely forecast. They use a susceptible–infected–removed (SIR) model with confinement (SCIR) to illustrate how lockdown measures inhibit infection spread only above a threshold. The existence of that threshold has major effects in predictability: A Bayesian fit to the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain shows that a slowdown in the number of newly infected individuals during the expansion phase allows one to infer neither the precise position of the maximum nor whether the measures taken will bring the propagation to the inhibition regime.

They warn against precise forecasts of the evolution of epidemics based on mean-field, effective, or phenomenological models and supports that only probabilities of different outcomes can be confidently given.

COVID-19 and Media datasets: Period – and location-specific textual data mining

Mathieu Roche

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2020.106356>

The vocabulary used in news on a disease such as COVID-19 changes according to the period. This aspect is discussed based on MEDISYS-sourced media datasets via two studies. The first focuses on terminology extraction and the second on period prediction according to the textual content using machine learning approaches.

September 24, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Modeling between population variation in COVID-19 dynamics in Hubei, Lombardy, and New York City

Bryan Wilder, Marie Charpignon, Jackson A. Killian et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2010651117>

The authors develop an individual-level model for SARS-CoV-2 transmission that accounts for location-dependent distributions of age, household structure, and comorbidities. They use these distributions for Hubei, China; Lombardy, Italy; and New York City, United States. Using data on reported deaths to obtain a posterior distribution over unknown parameters, they infer differences in the progression of the epidemic. They also examine the role of transmission due to particular age groups on total infections and deaths.

September 22, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Transmission dynamics reveal the impracticality of COVID-19 herd immunity strategies

Tobias S. Brett & Pejman Rohani

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2008087117>

The researchers used an age-structured transmission model, parameterized to simulate SARS-CoV-2 transmission in the United Kingdom, they assessed the long-term prospects of success using both of these approaches. They

simulated a range of different nonpharmaceutical intervention scenarios incorporating social distancing applied to different age groups. Their modeling confirmed that suppression of SARS-CoV-2 transmission is possible with social distancing over months, consistent with observed trends. Their modelling did not support achieving herd immunity.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

October 23, 2020 (Journal of Public Affairs)

Socioeconomic determinants of COVID-19 in Asian countries: An empirical analysis

Rittu S. Varkey, Justin Joy, Gargee Sarmah et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/pa.2532>

In this article, the authors examine the socioeconomic determinants of the occurrence of COVID in Asian countries by considering data as of June 18, 2020, for 42 Asian countries. They find a positive significant association of per capita gross national income and net migration with the incidence of total COVID-19 cases and daily new cases. The size of net migration emerged to be a potential factor and positive in determining the total and new cases of COVID-19.

Of particular interest is the finding that while countries having a higher percentage of aged populations are more prone to be affected by the spread of the virus, the coefficient of this variable for Asian countries is not in the expected line. Making people more participatory and responsive in adhering to the social distancing norms in public and the workplace is significant. The authors suggest that more “people-centric” public health measures need to be focused on COVID management strategies.

October 10, 2020 (Public Health)

Putting the voices and insights of migrants and diverse ethnic groups at the centre of our response to COVID-19

Mayuri Gogoi, Richard Armitage, Gavin Brown et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2020.09.019>

This is a letter to the journal arguing for the subject of the title and funding bodies to adequately and equitably support migrant-focused research and promote inclusion of migrant- specific patient and public information and engagement (PPIE) activities in England.

October 2, 2020 (Health Policy and Technology)

The COVID-19 pandemic: Global health policy and technology responses in the making

Doowon Lee, Naomi Moy, Jonathan Tritter et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.10.001>

This Special Issue focuses on the initial health policy and technology interventions used to respond to the first wave¹ of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in over 25 countries.

The variety of pandemic responses are motivated by the political leadership and legislative controls; and shaped by national differences in health systems, pandemic plans, and available technology. Responses are said to have been informed by existing and forecasted shortage of ICU units, prior experience of respiratory diseases, and the availability of contact tracing apps leading to limited and lagged data to inform policy. Several insights are made on the decisions made by governments, the effects of the COVID-19 and the subsequent impact on health and economic outcomes, The COVID-19 trends (Jan to Aug 2020), policy interventions and responses by organisations and governments, the impact of interventions on the economy and the interventions to support the economy.

September 1, 2020 (Social Sciences & Humanities Open)

Towards a comprehensive narrative and response to COVID-19 in Southeast Asia

Rosalia Sciortino & Fabio Saini.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100058>

This article makes a plea for sustained incorporation of wider social science and humanities learning, as opposed to primarily epidemiology-informed proposals in responses to COVID-19 in Southeast Asia. They argue that: “as social scientists and practitioners, they should reject the ideological platform of the so-called ‘new normal’ that predicates change only in terms of continued exertion of control and induced epidemiological society after lockdowns. They argue for transformative reforms for equitable and sustainable development, restructure our relations in society and with the environment. They advocate the use of simple language to better communicate with the public.